

Adsorption of Lower Monohydric Aliphatic Alcohols at the Mercury-Aqueous Acid Solution Interface and Their Corrosion Inhibition Property**

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Some lower monohydric aliphatic alcohols have been investigated for their inhibition effects on the corrosion of mild steel in 1N sulphuric acid solution at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$. The adsorption behaviour of these compounds at the mercury-aqueous acid solution interface has also been investigated from electrocapillary measurements; and dependence of the adsorption on structure and concentration of the adsorbate and on potential and charge at the mercury-solution interface has been discussed. The relationship between adsorbability of these organic derivatives on mercury and their inhibitive efficiency in acid corrosion of mild steel has been studied using a scale of electric-charge, known as "phi-scale of electrode potentials", which gives a possibility for the electrocapillary data to be used for study of inhibitors' action. The mechanism of inhibition action as a function of adsorption of the alcohols and their steric configuration has been discussed.

It has been shown that on the basis of *phi-scale of potentials*¹ a relationship between adsorption of nitrogen containing organic compounds on Hg and their inhibition efficiency in acid corrosion of Fe can be derived^{2,3,4}. Moreover, it appeared that the parallelism between the surface activity of organic compounds on Hg and their inhibition efficiency in acid corrosion of iron manifests itself also in the similar dependence of these two properties on structure of organic compounds^{2,5,6}. A systematic study of organic compounds belonging to different homologous series, therefore, becomes important; and the present investigation deals with aliphatic monohydric alcohols as surface active and corrosion inhibitive agents in corrosion of mild steel in 1 N H₂SO₄ solution at 25°.

Experimental

Finely polished stress free mild steel coupons of 20 mm × 15 mm × 0.1 mm size, obtained from the same sheet, having chemical composition as C, 0.09; Mn, 0.5; Si, 0.08; P, 0.04; and S, 0.04 (%) were used for finding the corrosion rates. Solutions of 1 N H₂SO₄ (AnalaR) and of alcohols (A.R.) of required concentrations were prepared in conductivity water (specific conductance $< 3 \times 10^{-6}$ ohms⁻¹. cm⁻¹ at 18°C). 1 N KCl (AnalaR) solution was used for calibration of the capillary tube of the electrometer filled with cleaned, dried and freshly distilled Hg (AnalaR).

The rates of corrosion of iron in 10 ml of 1 N H₂SO₄ solution for a duration of an optimum

period of 24 hours in absence and in presence of varying concentrations of alcohols were measured in a thermostat at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$ by classical weight loss method; and on this basis the values of the inhibition coefficients, K where,

$$K = \frac{i_0}{i_1} \quad \dots (1)$$

(*i*₀ and *i*₁ are rates of corrosion in absence and in presence of alcohols respectively) were calculated.

The interfacial tension measurements were carried out by means of a capillary electrometer made by Pyrex glass after the model of Antropov and Banerjee⁴ in an air-cooled room ($25 \pm 2^\circ$) using the same experimental procedure as described therein. All electrocapillary measurements were carried out in 1 N H₂SO₄ solution in absence and in presence of different amounts of alcohols; and a typical of these is plotted in Fig. 1.

The decrease in the rate of corrosion observed in the presence of alcohols satisfies fairly well the empirical equation⁴,

$$\log K = \text{const.}_K + \beta_K \log C \quad \dots (2)$$

where, *const.*_K and *β*_K are constants typical of a given compound and C, the volume concentration of the additive. At the 'phi-potential' of Hg equal to -0.26 V, which is the mean value of the corrosion

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Fig. 1. Electrocapillary curves for Iso-Propyl alcohol at different molar concentration in 1-N H_2SO_4 solution.

(1) 0.00 (2) 0.625M (3) 1.25M
(4) 2.5M (5) 4.0M (6) 5.0M

(The electrocapillary graphs for rest of the five compounds were found to follow the same trend.)

potential of Fe in 1 N H_2SO_4 solution in *phi-scale*^{3,4} (represented as ϕ_c by dotted line in Fig. 1), nearly all experimental points of the electrocapillary curves (e.c.c.) may be described by the equation⁴,

$$\log \Delta \gamma = \text{const.}_\gamma + \beta_\gamma \log C \quad \dots (3)$$

where, $\Delta \gamma$ denotes decrease of surface tension on Hg/H_2SO_4 (1 N) interface, and const._γ and β_γ are constants specified for a given compound at the given value (-0.26 V) of 'phi-potential'. The values of const._x , β_x , const._γ and β_γ , calculated from plot of $\log K$ against $\log C$ and from plot of \log

$\Delta \gamma$ against $\log C$ at $\phi_c = -0.26$ V are collected in Table 1. It can be seen that, for compounds

TABLE 1—VALUES OF 'CONSTANTS' OF EQN. 2 AND EQN. 3 (AT $\phi_c = -0.26$ V)

Nos.	Compounds	β_x	Const. _x	β_γ	Const. _γ
1.	Methyl alcohol	0.26	-0.078	1.45	0.065
2.	Ethyl alcohol	0.42	-0.053	1.40	0.730
*3.	N-Propyl alcohol	0.37	-0.010	0.37	1.387
*4.	Iso-Propyl alcohol	0.54	-0.074	0.53	1.262
*5.	N-Butyl alcohol	0.45	+0.235	0.46	1.636
*6.	Iso-Butyl alcohol	0.47	+0.190	0.48	1.573

marked with asterisks in the table $\beta_x = \beta_\gamma$; and in these cases a relationship between const._x and const._γ can be expressed by the equation,

$$\text{const.}_x = -1.36 + \text{const.}_\gamma \quad \dots (4)$$

A combination of equations (2), (3) and (4), gives an expression viz. $\log K = -1.36 + \text{const.}_\gamma + \beta_\gamma \log C$... (5)

for compounds with $\beta_x = \beta_\gamma$. The parallelism between inhibition coefficient, K and surface activity, $\Delta \gamma$ and also the coincidence of the values of β_x and β_γ , suggests the possibility of calculating from electrocapillary data, inhibition coefficients for these aliphatic monohydric alcohols from eqn. (5). (refer Table 2, columns 2-4)

TABLE 2—(i) VALUES OF INHIBITION COEFFICIENTS, K (eqn. 1) AND OF SURFACE TENSION DEPRESSION, $\Delta \gamma$ (AT $\phi_c = -0.26$ V) AT VARIOUS CONCENTRATIONS, C OF THE INHIBITORS (ii) COMPARISON OF VALUES OF K FOUND EXPERIMENTALLY (COLUMN 2) AND CALCULATED THEORETICALLY (COLUMN 3) (EQN. 5)

(1) C, M ($\Delta \gamma$, Dynes cm^{-1})	(2) C, M (K, expt)	(3) K, theo.	(4) Deviation (\pm %)
Methyl Alcohol (No. 1)			
2.1 (3.5)	1.0 (1.131)		Abnormal deviation Here $\beta_x \neq \beta_\gamma$ (refer Table 1)
3.0 (5.5)	2.0 (1.086)		
4.0 (8.5)	3.0 (1.121)		
5.0 (12.5)	4.0 (1.200)		
—	4.5 (1.198)		
—	5.0 (1.235)		
Ethyl Alcohol (No. 2)			
0.675 (3.25)	1.4 (1.107)		Abnormal deviation Here $\beta_x \neq \beta_\gamma$
1.125 (6.5)	1.6 (1.081)		
1.5 (9.5)	1.8 (1.123)		
2.0 (13.5)	2.0 (1.176)		
—	2.2 (1.231)		
N-Propyl Alcohol (No. 3)			
0.625 (19.25)	1.0 (1.078)	1.068	+ 0.93
1.25 (29.75)	1.5 (1.115)	1.239	-10.0
2.50 (37.25)	2.0 (1.139)	1.380	-17.4
4.0 (38.75)	3.0 (1.330)	1.606	-17.2
5.0 (40.25)	4.0 (1.864)	1.789	+ 4.1
—	5.0 (2.141)	1.945	+10.0
Iso-Propyl Alcohol (No. 4)			
0.625 (12.75)	1.0 (1.127)	1.253	-10.0
1.25 (22.00)	2.0 (1.298)	1.151	+13.7
2.50 (31.00)	3.0 (1.598)	1.396	+14.5
4.00 (35.25)	4.0 (1.706)	1.663	+ 2.5
5.00 (36.25)	4.5 (1.888)	1.770	+ 6.6

(Table 2 Contd.)

N-Butyl Alcohol (No. 5)				
0.22 (22.75)	0.40 (1.087)	1.234	-11.9	
0.315 (27.00)	0.48 (1.118)	1.343	-16.7	
0.45 (31.00)	0.56 (1.222)	1.442	-15.2	
0.60 (35.25)	0.72 (1.691)	1.622	+ 4.2	
0.80 (39.50)	0.80 (1.589)	1.702	- 6.6	
Iso-Butyl Alcohol (No. 6)				
0.264 (20.0)	0.416 (1.036)	1.072	- 3.4	
0.352 (22.5)	0.4998 (1.110)	1.170	- 5.1	
0.469 (26.75)	0.6664 (1.274)	1.314	- 5.2	
0.625 (30.50)	0.7497 (1.250)	1.422	-12.1	
0.833 (35.50)	—	—	—	

The charge on the Hg surface, qM in contact with experimental solutions at each potential was obtained by differentiation of electrocapillary curves with respect to potential and is shown in Fig.2*.

The surface excess, Γ is proportional to $-\frac{\delta\gamma}{\delta\log C}$, if the activity coefficient of the alcohol can be assumed constant over concentration range studied. The surface excess values of some alcohols on the Hg surface in 1 N H_2SO_4 solution at each potential were determined from a plot of γ against $\log C$. The variations of surface excess, Γ as a function of

Fig. 2. Dependence of the mercury electrode charge on the potential in 1-N H_2SO_4 solution with different additions of (A) Methyl alcohol (B) Ethyl alcohol (C) N-propyl alcohol (D) Iso-Propyl alcohol (E) N-Butyl alcohol (F) Iso-Butyl alcohol. (Concentration stated on figures)

* In Fig. 2 the variation of surface charge with potential is shown for the highest and lowest concentrations only along with the curve for the base solution in order to avoid crowding the plot.

surface charge, q_M at a few concentrations of alcohols are given in Fig. 3†.

Fig. 3. Variation of adsorption of inhibitors with charge on the mercury electrode in 1-N H_2SO_4 solution with different additions of 1(A & B): Methyl alcohol, 2(A & B): N-Butyl alcohol, and 3(A & B): Iso-Butyl alcohol. (Concentration stated on the figure)

Results and Discussion

It may be observed from the various curves (Figs. 1, 2 and 3) that (i) alcohols have a general tendency to be adsorbed at the negative potentials and desorbed at the positive potentials on the mercury surface, (ii) adsorption increases with the increase of their bulk concentration as well as with increase in the n -alkyl chain length of the hydrocarbon end and (iii) alcohols have a tendency to desorb at the extreme positive/negative charge on the mercury surface.

It can be seen from Table 2 that (i) at the same molar concentration of alcohols, inhibitive efficiency for the corrosion of mild steel in 1 N H_2SO_4 solution and the degree of adsorption on mercury in the same solution at $E_{e\phi C}$ increases essentially in the same order for the substances examined, (ii) with increasing concentration, the increase of effectiveness of the inhibition parallels an increase the surface adsorption and (iii) in the homologous series the corrosion inhibition increases due to decreasing solubility and increasing adsorbability resulting from increasing n -alkyl chain length°. It is further observed that (Table 2, col. 1) surface activity at the Hg/solution interface is somewhat more in case of n -alcohols than in iso-alcohols; and this may be due to the presence of more methylene group in the former than in the latter, and the strong interaction between the CH_2 group and the negatively charged Hg surface. Furthermore, n -alcohols are less soluble than iso-alcohols and due to 'squeezing type' effect it would be more adsorbed on the metal surface.

† In Fig 3 the values were plotted for three alcohols viz. methyl alcohol, n -butyl alcohol and iso-butyl alcohol only, and each at two concentrations. The same trend has been found to follow at other concentrations and for other alcohols.

The preferential adsorption of alcohols on the negatively charged surface than on the positively charged surface may be due to stronger coulombic interaction between positively charged hydrocarbon radicals of the alcohols and the negatively charged Hg surface. It may be that alcohols as active neutral molecules, get adsorbed both at the anodic and cathodic sides of the *e.c.m.* with 'alkyl group' towards the metal surface and the 'hydroxyl end' towards the solution. Desorption of these alcohol molecules (ϵ , dielectric constant varying from 17.1 to 32.63 at 25°) with low polarizability at the anodic branches is, therefore, due to stronger attraction of the water molecules (ϵ_{H_2O} , 78.54 at 25°) with high polarizability through the oxygen atom and the weaker interaction of the positively charged 'alkyl end' of the dipole on the positively charged metal surface. Strong adsorption on the cathodic side, on the contrary, indicates stronger electrostatic interaction of the paraffinic end resulting parallel orientation on the Hg surface, and the weaker attraction of the water molecules through the 'hydrogen atoms' on the negatively charged surface.

A progressive increase in the length of the aliphatic chain would increase the basicity of the molecule due to the inductive effect of the methylene groups, and it would acquire somewhat more positive character and as a result would be adsorbed more effectively on the negatively charged metal surface. The lower alcohols are, therefore, expected to be inclined to the metal surface covering lesser area, while the higher ones to be more flat covering areas proportional to the molecular dimensions of the adsorbates. The decrease in inhibition observed on substitution of the branched alkyl chain for a straight one is due to the fact that the 'methyl group' in the iso-compound prevent close contact of the neighbouring adsorbed molecules, and as a result, not only is adsorption decreased but also the closeness of packing of the molecules is reduced. Furthermore, lesser inhibition action of the iso-alcohols over the corresponding n -alcohols even with having a higher electron charge on the oxygen atom may be due to the fact that, the oxygen is screened by the 'methyl' group as a result of the steric configuration of the former; and thus unable to attach itself stably on the iron surface.

The general correlation, as noted above, between the surface coverage on Hg and the inhibitive efficiency of the alcohols (Nos. 3 to 6, Table 2) on the corrosion of iron in acid media suggests, in general, that for these stable organic compounds, the inhibition efficiency is broadly dependent on the adsorption of these organic compounds on the corroding metal surface due to the electrostatic interaction, and hence specific attachment to the 'active centres' on the electrode surface is of no primary importance°. Abnormal behaviour of the methyl and ethyl alcohols may be due to the weak electrostatic interaction resulting from the poor dipolar nature of these molecules.

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References

1. L. I. ANTROPOV, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **35**, 309.
2. L. I. ANTROPOV and S. N. BANERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 451.
3. L. I. ANTROPOV, *J. Phy. Chem*, U. S. S. R., (Eng. Trans.), 1963, **37**, 507.
4. L. I. ANTROPOV and S. N. BANERJEE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **35**, 531.
5. L. I. ANTROPOV, V. P. GRIGORIEV and A. T. PETRENKO, *Ann. Inst. Polytech., Novotcherkassk*, 1958, **69/83**, 129.
6. E. BLOMGREN, J. O'M. BOCKRIS and C. JESCH, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1961, **65**, 2000.
7. C. D. HODGMAN (Ed), "*Handbook of Chemistry and Physics*", The Chemical Rubber Publ. Co., 42nd. Edn., p. 2514.
8. N. HACKERMAN and R. M. HURD, *First International Cong. on Metallic Corrosion*, London, Butterworths, 1961, p. 166.